

Neutrosophic assessment of evidence in cases of divorce due to adultery: An application of the OWA-TOPSIS model to the evidentiary obstacle in the Ecuadorian legal system

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Abstract. The current research resolves an internal issue of the Ecuadorian legal system: the assessment of evidence for divorce by adultery, an unjust approach since it cannot always be evidenced properly. Thus, when judges have the power to rule, their authority is compromised since one of the most crucial elements of adjudicatory due process is equity, and equity stems from objectivity. Unfortunately, we see subjectivity here stemming from the uncertainty and indeterminacy relative to such evidence. While much literature exists relative to the analysis of judicial determination, little evolution occurs relative to a solid approach that incorporates such uncertainty and indeterminacy relative to evidence used within judicial family matters. Thus, we propose an approach via neutrosophic OWA-TOPSIS model parameters. This is a novel contribution to family justice jurisdiction as it allows all ambiguity and uncertainty to be assessed objectively via wafts or evincing legitimizing explanations. For example, we use a case study where we fuzzify the evidence—chats, behavior, testimonials—and convert them to levels of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity. Then, following this neutrosophic approach, we assess competing hypotheses for adultery based on neutrosophic evidence and provide a distinct ranking of options. We contribute to the literature both theoretically and practically. Theoretically, we provide a multi-criteria judicial investigatory measure where none existed before; practically, we provide the judge/lawyer an unimpeachable solution with which complicated assessments can be calculated with greater judicial efficiency and effectiveness in less time and converted into assessment criteria that lessen the evidentiary threshold which for years has caused too much debate in Ecuadorian family justice.

Keywords: Divorce, adultery, evidence, neutrosophy, OWA-TOPSIS, Ecuador, legal decision.

1. Introduction.

The dissolution of marriage due to adultery constitutes an area of particular relevance in the Ecuadorian judicial system, demanding an in-depth analysis of the evidence to safeguard the principles of justice and equity. The correct assessment of evidence in these proceedings is crucial, as it directly impacts the lives of those involved, determining not only the marital status but also financial and parental aspects of considerable significance [1]. Despite its importance, proof of adultery often presents unique challenges due to its inherently discreet nature, requiring a thorough scrutiny of the evidence and circumstances.

Historically, the divorce process has evolved from restrictive conceptions rooted in canonical regulations to more liberal and causal approaches [2]. In the Latin American context, and specifically in Ecuador, adultery has persisted as a determining cause, which has generated extensive jurisprudence

around the interpretation of indirect evidence and the construction of judicial conviction [3], [4]. However, the interpretation of the evidence in these cases, which is frequently limited to subjective indications and testimonies, introduces a degree of uncertainty that traditional methods of evidentiary assessment fail to address exhaustively [5].

The central problem that this research seeks to resolve lies in the absence of a structured methodological framework that allows for managing the uncertainty and ambiguity inherent in the proof of adultery in the Ecuadorian legal sphere. Conventional methods of evidentiary assessment, although fundamental, often lack the capacity to quantify or mitigate the indeterminacy present in human testimony or in the indirect nature of certain indications [6]. How can justice operators more rigorously and transparently evaluate the occurrence of adultery when the available evidence is fragmented, inconsistent, or subjective, and the law requires a precise assessment? This methodological gap results in judicial decisions that, although legitimate, can be perceived as lacking a solid analytical basis in the face of doubt. Subjectivity in the interpretation of evidence can lead to inconsistencies and a perception of arbitrariness, undermining confidence in the judicial system [7]. Therefore, it is imperative to develop tools that allow for more systematic management of uncertain information, fostering greater objectivity in the assessment of evidence.

Uncertainty not only affects the evidence phase but also permeates the judicial decision-making phase, where judges must weigh multiple factors and evidence with varying degrees of reliability [8]. In this scenario, the application of mathematical approaches that model imprecision and ambiguity can offer a significant advantage. This is where neutrosophic logic, with its ability to represent degrees of truth, falsity, and indeterminacy, emerges as a promising alternative.

Several studies have begun to explore the application of multi-criteria decision-making models in the field of law, mainly in areas such as damage assessment or the selection of judicial personnel [9]. However, their incursion into the specific field of evidence assessment in divorce proceedings based on adultery, where ambiguity is a preponderant factor, is still limited. This research proposes an innovative solution to the identified problem. In this context, the present study proposes the application of the neutrosophic OWA-TOPSIS model as an effective tool for the assessment of evidence in divorce trials based on adultery in Ecuador. This approach will allow the quantification and processing of the uncertainty associated with the different pieces of evidence, facilitating a more structured and objective assessment. The methodology employed will include the study of a practical case, where neutrosophic values will be assigned to the clues and testimonies, and the model will be applied to generate a ranking of hypotheses regarding the occurrence of adultery.

In line with the above, the objectives of this study are: (1) to develop an evidentiary assessment model based on the neutrosophic OWA-TOPSIS approach for divorce cases based on adultery in the Ecuadorian legal system; and (2) to demonstrate, through a case study, the viability and usefulness of this model in overcoming evidentiary obstacles associated with the indeterminacy and ambiguity of indirect evidence.

2. Preliminaries.

2.1. Evidentiary Obstacle in the Legal System.

The legal system, in its pursuit of justice, fundamentally relies on evidence. This constitutes the foundation upon which judicial decisions are built, as it is through it that the facts are established and procedural truth is verified. However, in practice, obtaining and evaluating evidence is not always a path free of difficulties, sometimes becoming a real evidentiary obstacle. This impediment not only delays proceedings but can ultimately compromise the effectiveness of justice, generating dissatisfaction and distrust among citizens. The nature of this obstacle is multifaceted. Sometimes it lies in the inaccessibility of evidence, where crucial elements to clarify a fact are simply unavailable or have been destroyed. Other times, the difficulty lies in the vagueness or ambiguity of the information, as occurs with contradictory testimony or clues that do not offer unequivocal certainty. This type of scenario is particularly

pronounced in cases involving private conduct or illicit acts that are difficult to document, such as adultery or certain economic crimes.

A crucial aspect of the evidentiary obstacle is the inherent subjectivity of judicial assessment. Although judges are guided by principles of sound judgment and logic, the interpretation of evidence remains, to a certain extent, a human act influenced by individual experience and perception. This subjectivity can lead to inconsistencies in the application of the law and disparities in decisions, generating a sense of unpredictability in the system. The need for greater objectivity then becomes imperative. In addition to the above, the burden of proof represents a constant challenge. The party asserting a fact must prove it, and if the evidence is scarce or unconvincing, the outcome of the trial can be seriously affected. This is especially problematic in situations where privileged information or an imbalance of power between the parties makes it difficult to access the necessary evidence, leaving one party at a substantial disadvantage. Technological advancement, while promising for obtaining new forms of evidence, also introduces complexities. Digital evidence, for example, presents challenges regarding authenticity, integrity, and chain of custody. Determining whether a text message or email has been tampered with, or whether an electronic record is truly authentic, requires specialized technical expertise and up-to-date legal frameworks that don't always keep pace with the pace of innovation.

While jurisprudence has attempted to establish criteria for the assessment of indirect evidence and the construction of judicial conviction, it often encounters the limitation of uncertainty. Judgments, in their attempt to justify a decision, must navigate the delicate balance between the available evidence and the need to reach a threshold of certainty, which is not always easy in complex scenarios and with imprecise data. Therefore, the search for solutions to mitigate the evidentiary obstacle is an ongoing and multidisciplinary task. It is not simply a matter of reforming codes or procedures, but of incorporating tools and approaches that allow for more intelligent and rigorous management of uncertain and ambiguous information. The goal is to provide the judicial system with mechanisms that reinforce confidence in its rulings. In this context, multi-criteria decision-making methodologies and non-classical logics, such as neutrosophy, emerge as promising avenues. These approaches can provide an analytical framework for processing information under conditions of uncertainty, allowing for a more systematic assessment of different pieces of evidence. By assigning degrees of truth, uncertainty, and falsity, it is possible to capture the complexity of evidence in a way that binary approaches fail to do [10].

The implementation of these tools does not seek to replace the judge's wisdom or judgment, but rather to complement them, providing a more robust framework for justifying decisions. In fact, the integration of models such as the neutrosophic OWA-TOPSIS into evidentiary analysis can lead to greater transparency and consistency in the application of the law, reducing the perception of arbitrariness and increasing the legitimacy of judicial decisions [11], [12]. The adaptability of these techniques to different evidentiary contexts highlights their potential. Ultimately, overcoming the evidentiary obstacle in the legal system is not a utopia; it is a pressing need that demands the convergence of legal science with disciplines such as logic and artificial intelligence. Investment in the research and development of these methodologies is essential to ensure that justice is not only administered, but that it is administered with the greatest possible certainty and fairness, even in the face of the most elusive evidence [13], [14].

2.2. SVNS and SVNLS

This section provides a brief overview of the fundamental principles related to SVNS and SVNLS, covering definitions, operating principles, and metrics for measuring distances.

Definition 1. Let x be an element in a finite set, X . A single-valued neutrosophic set (SVNS), P , in X can be defined as in (1):

$$P = \{ x, T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x) | x \in X \}, \quad (1)$$

where the truth membership function, $T_p(x)$, the indeterminacy membership function $I_p(x)$, and the falsehood membership function $F_p(x)$ clearly adhere to condition (2):

$$0 \leq T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x) \leq 1; \quad 0 \leq T_p(x) + I_p(x) + F_p(x) \leq 3 \quad (2)$$

For a SVN S , P in X , we call the triplet $(T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x))$ its single-valued neutrosophic value (SVNV), denoted simply $x = (T_x, I_x, F_x)$ for computational convenience.

Definition 2. Let $x = (T_x, I_x, F_x)$ and $y = (T_y, I_y, F_y)$ be two SVNV. Then

- 1) $x \oplus y = (T_x + T_y - T_x * T_y, I_x * I_y, F_x * F_y)$;
- 2) $\lambda * x = (1 - (1 - T_x)\lambda, (I_x)\lambda, (F_x)\lambda), \lambda > 0$;
- 3) $x^\lambda = ((T_x)\lambda, 1 - (1 - I_x)\lambda, 1 - (1 - F_x)\lambda), \lambda > 0$

The linguistic set

Let l be $S = \{s_\alpha | \alpha = 1, \dots, l\}$ a finite, totally ordered discrete term with odd value, where s_α denotes a possible value for a linguistic variable. For example, if $l = 7$, then a set of linguistic terms S could be described as follows:

$$S = \{s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5, s_6, s_7\} = \{\text{extremely poor, very poor, poor, fair, good, very good, extremely good}\}. \quad (3)$$

Any linguistic variable, s_i or s_j , in S must satisfy the following rules:

- 1) $Neg(s_i) = s_{-i}$;
- 2) $s_i \leq s_j \Leftrightarrow i \leq j$;
- 3) $\max(s_i, s_j) = s_j$, if $i \leq j$;
- 4) $\min(s_i, s_j) = s_i$, if $i \leq j$.

To avoid information loss during an aggregation process, the discrete set of terms S will be extended to a continuous set of terms. $S = \{s_\alpha | \alpha \in R\}$. Any two linguistic variables $s_\alpha, s_\beta \in S$ satisfy the following operational laws [15,16] :

- 1) $s_\alpha \oplus s_\beta = s_{\alpha + \beta}$;
- 2) $\mu s_\alpha = s_{\mu\alpha}, \mu \geq 0$;
- 3) $\frac{s_\alpha}{s_\beta} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}$

Definition 3 [17] Given X , a finite set of universes, a SVNLS, P , in X can be defined as in (4):

$$P = \{ \langle x, [s_{\theta(x)}, (T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x))] \rangle | x \in X \} \quad (4)$$

where $s_{\theta(x)} \in \bar{S}$, the truth membership function $T_p(x)$, the indeterminacy membership function, $I_p(x)$ and the falsehood membership function $F_p(x)$ satisfy condition (5):

$$0 \leq T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x) \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq T_p(x) + I_p(x) + F_p(x) \leq 3. \quad (5)$$

For an SVNLS, P , in X , the 4- $\langle s_{\theta(x)}, (T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x)) \rangle$ tuple is known as the Single-Valued Neutrosophic Linguistic Set (SVNLN), conveniently denoted $x = s_{\theta(x)}, (T_x, I_x, F_x)$ for computational purposes.

Definition 4 [17] . Let there be $x_i = \langle s_{\theta(x_i)}, (T_{x_i}, I_{x_i}, F_{x_i}) \rangle$ ($i = 1, 2$) two SVNLNs. Then

- 1) $x_1 \oplus x_2 = \langle s_{\theta(x_1) + \theta(x_2)}, (T_{x_1} + T_{x_2} - T_{x_1} * T_{x_2}, I_{x_1} * I_{x_2}, F_{x_1} * F_{x_2}) \rangle$
- 2) $\lambda x_1 = \langle s_{\lambda\theta(x_1)}, (1 - (1 - T_{x_1})^\lambda, (I_{x_1})^\lambda, (F_{x_1})^\lambda) \rangle, \lambda > 0$;
- 3) $x_1^\lambda = \langle s_{\theta^\lambda(x_1)}, ((T_{x_1})^\lambda, 1 - (1 - I_{x_1})^\lambda, 1 - (1 - F_{x_1})^\lambda) \rangle, \lambda > 0$.

Definition 5 [17] . Let there be $x_i = \langle s_{\theta(x_i)}, (T_{x_i}, I_{x_i}, F_{x_i}) \rangle$ ($i = 1, 2$) two SVNLSs. Their distance measure is defined as in (6):

$$d(x_1, x_2) = \left[|s_{\theta(x_1)} T_{x_1} - s_{\theta(x_2)} T_{x_2}|^\mu + |s_{\theta(x_1)} I_{x_1} - s_{\theta(x_2)} I_{x_2}|^\mu + |s_{\theta(x_1)} F_{x_1} - s_{\theta(x_2)} F_{x_2}|^\mu \right]^{\frac{1}{\mu}} \quad (6)$$

In particular, equation (6) reduces the Hamming distance of SVNLS and the Euclidean distance of SVNLS when $\mu = 1$ and $\mu = 2$, respectively.

2.3. MADM Based on the SVNLOWAD-TOPSIS Method

For a given multi-attribute decision-making problem in SNVL environments, $A = \{A_1, \dots, A_m\}$ denotes a set of discrete feasible alternatives, $C = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ represents a set of attributes, and $E = \{e_1, \dots, e_k\}$ is a set of experts (or DMs) with weight vector $\omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_k\}^T$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $0 \leq \omega_i \leq 1$. Suppose that the attribute weight vector is $s v = (v_1, \dots, v_n)^T$, which satisfies $\sum_{i=1}^n v_i = 1$ and $v_i \in [0, 1]$. The evaluation, $\alpha_{ij}^{(k)}$ given by the expert, $e_{t(t=1, \dots, k)}$ on the alternative, $A_{i(i=1, \dots, m)}$, relative to the attribute, $C_{j(j=1, \dots, n)}$ forms the individual decision matrix as shown in equation (7):

$$D^k = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & \dots & C_n \\ A_1 & \alpha_{11}^{(k)} & \dots & \alpha_{1n}^{(k)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_n & \alpha_{n1}^{(k)} & \dots & \alpha_{nn}^{(k)} \end{matrix} \quad (7)$$

where $\alpha_{ij}^k = \langle s_{\theta(\alpha_{ij})}^k, (T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k) \rangle$ is represented by a SVNLS, which satisfies $s_{\theta(\alpha_{ij})}^k \in \bar{S}, T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k \in [0, 1]$ and $0 \leq T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k + I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k + F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k \leq 3$.

Geng et al. [18] extended the TOPSIS method to fit the SVNLS scenario, and the procedures of the extended model can be summarized as follows.

Step 1. Normalize the individual decision matrices:

In practical scenarios, MADM problems can encompass both benefit attributes and cost attributes. Let B and S the benefit attribute sets and cost attribute sets, respectively. Therefore, the conversion rules specified in (8) apply:

$$\begin{cases} r_{ij}^{(k)} = \alpha_{ij}^{(k)} = \langle s_{\theta(\alpha_{ij})}^k, (T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k) \rangle, & \text{for } j \in B, \\ r_{ij}^{(k)} = \langle s_{1-\theta(\alpha_{ij})}^k, (T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k) \rangle, & \text{for } j \in S. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Thus, the standardized decision information, $R^k = (r_{ij}^{(k)})_{m \times n}$, is set as in (9):

$$R^k = (r_{ij}^{(k)})_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} r_{11}^{(k)} & \dots & r_{1n}^{(k)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{m1}^{(k)} & \dots & r_{mn}^{(k)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Step 2. Build the collective matrix:

All individual DM reviews are aggregated into a group review:

$$R = (r_{ij})_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} r_{11} & \dots & r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{m1} & \dots & r_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Where $r_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^t \omega_k r_{ij}^{(k)}$.

Step 3. Set the weighted SVNLS decision information:

The weighted SVNLS decision matrix, \tilde{R} , is formed as shown in (11), using the operational laws given in Definition 2 above:

$$Y = (y_{ij})_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} v_1 r_{11} & \cdots & v_n r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ v_1 r_{m1} & \cdots & v_n r_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The OWA operator is fundamental in aggregation techniques, widely studied by researchers [18]. Its main advantage lies in organizing arguments and facilitating the integration of experts' attitudes in decision making. Recent research has explored OWA in distance measurement, generating variations of OWAD [17]. Taking advantage of the benefits of OWA, the text proposes a SVNLOWAD distance measure (SVNLOWAD). Given the desirable properties of the OWA operator, an SVNLOWAD distance measure (SVNLOWAD) is proposed in the following text.

Definition 6. Let x_j, x'_j ($j = 1, \dots, n$) the two collections be SVNLN. If

$$SVNLOWAD((x_1, x'_1), \dots, (x_n, x'_n)) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j d(x_j, x'_j), \quad (12)$$

Therefore, step 4 of this method can be considered as follows:

Step 4. For each alternative, A_i the SVNLOWAD is calculated for the PIS, A^+ and the NIS A^- , using equation (12):

$$SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^+) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \check{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^+), i = 1, \dots, m \quad (13)$$

$$SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \check{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^-), i = 1, \dots, m \quad (14)$$

where $\check{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^+)$ and $\check{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^-)$ they are the j -th largest values of $d(y_{ij}, y_j^+)$ and $d(y_{ij}, y_j^-)$, respectively.

Step 5. In the classical TOPSIS approach, the relative closeness coefficient, C' , is used to rank the alternatives. However, some researchers have highlighted cases where relative closeness fails to achieve the desired objective of simultaneously minimizing the distance from the PIS and maximizing the distance from the NIS. Thus, following an idea proposed in references [15], in equations (15)–(17), we introduce a modified relative closeness coefficient, $C'(A_i)$, used to measure the degree to which the alternatives, A_i ($i = 1, \dots, m$), are close to the PIS and also far from the NIS, congruently:

$$C'(A_i) = \frac{SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-)}{SVNLOWAD_{\max}(A_i, A^-)} - \frac{SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^+)}{SVNLOWAD_{\min}(A_i, A^+)}, \quad (15)$$

where

$$SVNLOWAD_{\max}(A_i, A^-) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq m} SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-), \quad (16)$$

and

$$SVNLOWAD_{\min}(A_i, A^+) = \min_{1 \leq i \leq m} SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^+). \quad (17)$$

It is clear that $C'(A_i) \leq 0$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$) the higher the value of $C'(A_i)$ and, the better A_i the alternative. Furthermore, if an alternative A^* satisfies the conditions $SVNLOWAD(A^*, A^-) = SVNLOWAD_{\max}(A^*, A^-)$ and $SVNLOWAD(A^*, A^+) = SVNLOWAD_{\min}(A^*, A^+)$, then $C'(A^*) = 0$ and the alternative A^* is the most suitable candidate, since it has the minimum distance to the PIS and the maximum distance to the NIS.

Step 6. Rank and identify the most desirable alternatives based on the decreasing closeness coefficient $C'(A_i)$ obtained using Equation (15).

3. Case Study.

This study analyzes a divorce case based on adultery in the Ecuadorian judicial system, applying the neutrosophic OWA-TOPSIS model for the objective assessment of the evidence presented. The available evidence is evaluated to determine whether there is sufficient evidence to confirm the grounds for divorce.

Participants and methodology

Three judges specializing in family law participated in the study, evaluating the evidence presented according to established criteria. The neutrosophic OWA-TOPSIS model was applied to integrate the individual evaluations and obtain an objective collective assessment.

Evidence and evaluation criteria

Four types of evidence presented in the case were considered:

- **Alternative A1 (Electronic Messages):** Instant messaging conversations between the respondent spouse and third parties.
- **Alternative A2 (Testimonies):** Statements from witnesses who witnessed compromising conduct.
- **Alternative A3 (Photographs):** Images showing meetings of the defendant spouse with third parties.
- **Alternative A4 (Location logs):** Geolocation data extracted from mobile devices.

The evaluation criteria used were:

- **C1. Authenticity (AU):** Degree to which the evidence is verifiably genuine.
- **C2. Relevance (PE):** Relevance of the evidence to the specific case.
- **C3. Conduciveness (CO) :** Capacity of the evidence to effectively demonstrate adultery.
- **C4. Legality (LI):** Conformity of the evidence with procedural and constitutional norms.

The judges assigned weights to the criteria according to their relative importance: $C_1: 0,15, C_2: 0,25, C_3: 0,25$ y $C_4: 0,35$.

Evaluation and decision matrices

The evaluations were expressed using Neutrosophic Values of Language (SVNL) with the following scale: $S = \{s_1 = \text{"extremely poor"}, s_2 = \text{"very poor"}, s_3 = \text{"poor"}, s_4 = \text{"acceptable"}, s_5 = \text{"good"}, s_6 = \text{"very good"}, s_7 = \text{"extremely good"}\}$

The standardized SVNL decision matrices are presented below:

Table 1: Evaluation of evidence according to Criterion 1 (Authenticity)

Evidence	Judge 1	Judge 2	Judge 3
A ₁	S ₅ (0.4; 0.2; 0.3)	S ₅ (0.4; 0.3; 0.4)	S ₆ (0.5; 0.2; 0.3)
A ₂	S ₆ (0.6; 0.1; 0.2)	S ₆ (0.7; 0.2; 0.3)	S ₅ (0.5; 0.2; 0.3)
A ₃	S ₅ (0.4; 0.3; 0.4)	S ₆ (0.4; 0.2; 0.4)	S ₆ (0.5; 0.1; 0.3)
A ₄	S ₆ (0.7; 0.2; 0.3)	S ₄ (0.8; 0.1; 0.2)	S ₄ (0.6; 0.1; 0.2)

Table 2: Evidence evaluation according to Criterion 2 (Relevance)

Evidence	Judge 1	Judge 2	Judge 3
A ₁	S ₅ (0.4; 0.2; 0.3)	S ₆ (0.5; 0.1; 0.2)	S ₆ (0.6; 0.2; 0.4)
A ₂	S ₅ (0.6; 0.1; 0.2)	S ₆ (0.7; 0.2; 0.3)	S ₄ (0.7; 0.2; 0.2)
A ₃	S ₄ (0.5; 0.2; 0.3)	S ₆ (0.6; 0.3; 0.4)	S ₅ (0.6; 0.1; 0.3)
A ₄	S ₄ (0.6; 0.1; 0.2)	S ₅ (0.7; 0.2; 0.3)	S ₄ (0.5; 0.2; 0.2)

Table 3: Evidence evaluation according to Criterion 3 (Conduciveness)

Evidence	Judge 1	Judge 2	Judge 3
A ₁	S ₃ (0.3; 0.2; 0.5)	S ₅ (0.3; 0.1; 0.6)	S ₅ (0.2; 0.1; 0.6)
A ₂	S ₄ (0.5; 0.2; 0.2)	S ₅ (0.6; 0.2; 0.2)	S ₅ (0.7; 0.2; 0.1)
A ₃	S ₃ (0.5; 0.3; 0.1)	S ₄ (0.6; 0.1; 0.3)	S ₄ (0.6; 0.2; 0.1)
A ₄	S ₃ (0.3; 0.1; 0.2)	S ₄ (0.4; 0.2; 0.2)	S ₃ (0.4; 0.1; 0.1)

Table 4: Evaluation of evidence according to Criterion 4 (Legality)

Evidence	Judge 1	Judge 2	Judge 3
A ₁	S ₄ (0.5; 0.3; 0.3)	S ₃ (0.7; 0.1; 0.1)	S ₄ (0.5; 0.2; 0.3)
A ₂	S ₃ (0.6; 0.2; 0.4)	S ₄ (0.5; 0.4; 0.2)	S ₆ (0.4; 0.6; 0.2)
A ₃	S ₅ (0.3; 0.5; 0.2)	S ₅ (0.4; 0.4; 0.1)	S ₄ (0.3; 0.6; 0.2)
A ₄	S ₆ (0.6; 0.1; 0.2)	S ₆ (0.6; 0.3; 0.3)	S ₅ (0.7; 0.2; 0.1)

Collective decision matrix

The SVNL collective decision matrix, which integrates the individual evaluations of the three judges, is presented below:

Table 5: SVNL Collective Decision Matrix

Evidence	C ₁ (Authenticity)	C ₂ (Relevance)	C ₃ (Conductivity)	C ₄ (Legality)
A ₁	S _{5.33} (0.433; 0.233; 0.333)	S _{5.67} (0.500; 0.167; 0.300)	S _{4.33} (0.267; 0.133; 0.567)	S _{3.67} (0.567; 0.200; 0.233)
A ₂	S _{5.67} (0.600; 0.167; 0.267)	S _{5.00} (0.667; 0.167; 0.233)	S _{4.67} (0.600; 0.200; 0.167)	S _{4.33} (0.500; 0.400; 0.267)
A ₃	S _{5.67} (0.433; 0.200; 0.367)	S _{5.00} (0.567; 0.200; 0.333)	S _{3.67} (0.567; 0.200; 0.167)	S _{4.67} (0.333; 0.500; 0.167)
A ₄	S _{4.67} (0.700; 0.133; 0.233)	S _{4.33} (0.600; 0.167; 0.233)	S _{3.33} (0.367; 0.133; 0.167)	S _{5.67} (0.633; 0.200; 0.200)

Weighted collective decision matrix

By applying the criteria weights (C₁: 0.15, C₂: 0.25, C₃: 0.25, C₄: 0.35),the weighted collective SVNL decision matrix is obtained:

Table 6: Weighted collective SVNL decision matrix

Evidence	C ₁ (Authenticity)	C ₂ (Relevance)	C ₃ (Conductivity)	C ₄ (Legality)
A ₁	S _{0.80} (0.065; 0.348; 0.433)	S _{1.42} (0.125; 0.367; 0.475)	S _{1.08} (0.067; 0.350; 0.675)	S _{1.28} (0.198; 0.430; 0.452)
A ₂	S _{0.85} (0.090; 0.292; 0.377)	S _{1.25} (0.167; 0.375; 0.425)	S _{1.17} (0.150; 0.400; 0.375)	S _{1.52} (0.175; 0.610; 0.523)
A ₃	S _{0.85} (0.065; 0.320; 0.462)	S _{1.25} (0.142; 0.400; 0.500)	S _{0.92} (0.142; 0.400; 0.375)	S _{1.63} (0.117; 0.675; 0.458)
A ₄	S _{0.70} (0.105; 0.263; 0.348)	S _{1.08} (0.150; 0.375; 0.425)	S _{0.83} (0.092; 0.350; 0.375)	S _{1.98} (0.222; 0.430; 0.430)

Positive ideal solution (PIS) and negative ideal solution (NIS)

For each criterion, the positive ideal solution (PIS) is determined as the maximum value for the truth component and the minimum values for the indeterminacy and falsity components. The negative ideal solution (NIS) is determined inversely.

PIS (A⁺):

- C1: (0.105, 0.263, 0.348)
- C2: (0.167, 0.367, 0.425)
- C3: (0.150, 0.350, 0.375)
- C4: (0.222, 0.430, 0.452)

NIS (A⁻):

- C1: (0.065, 0.348, 0.462)
- C2: (0.125, 0.400, 0.500)
- C3: (0.067, 0.400, 0.675)
- C4: (0.117, 0.675, 0.523)

Calculation of relative distances

The judges determined the OWA operator weight vector as $W = (0.25, 0.30, 0.35, 0.10)$, reflecting their attitudes toward the relative importance of the criteria.

Using neutrosophic distances and the OWA operator, the distances between each alternative and the positive (PIS) and negative (NIS) reference points were calculated:

Table 7: Relative distances between each evidence and the reference points

Evidence	SVNLOWAD(A _i , A ⁺)	SVNLOWAD(A _i , A ⁻)	C
A ₁	0.127	0.135	0.515
A ₂	0.037	0.081	0.686
A ₃	0.070	0.117	0.626
A ₄	0.070	0.005	0.067

Where C is the coefficient of relative closeness calculated as: $C = \frac{SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-)}{[SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^+) + SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-)]}$

Chart 1: Relative distances between each piece of evidence and the reference points. Analysis of results

The results obtained through the neutrosophic OWA-TOPSIS model provide a systematic and objective assessment of the evidence presented in the case of divorce due to adultery.

The distances $SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^+)$ represent the proximity of each type of evidence to the positive ideal point, with lower values indicating greater proximity to the ideal solution. In this regard, Alternative A₂ (Testimonies) has the lowest value (0.037), followed by Alternatives A₃ and A₄ (Photographs and Location Records) with 0.070 each, and finally Alternative A₁ (Electronic Messages) with 0.127.

On the other hand, the distances $SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-)$ measure the distance of each piece of evidence from the negative ideal point, where higher values are preferable. Alternative A₁ shows the highest value (0.135), followed by A₃ (0.117) and A₂ (0.081), while A₄ presents the lowest value (0.005).

The relative closeness coefficient (C) integrates both distances to provide a single rating index. The higher this value, the more desirable the alternative. The results show that Alternative A₂ (Testimonies) has the highest value (0.686), indicating that it is the most robust evidence according to the evaluated criteria. It is followed by Alternative A₃ (Photographs) with 0.626, Alternative A₁ (Electronic Messages) with 0.515, and finally Alternative A₄ (Location Records) with 0.067.

4. Conclusions

Based on the data presented in the study, here is a rewritten conclusion in English that resolves the previously identified errors:

The analysis shows that the neutrosophic OWA-TOPSIS model provides a clear and systematic ranking of the evidence presented in this specific case study. According to the calculated relative closeness coefficient (C), Testimonial evidence (A₂) was identified as the most robust and effective evidence to support the grounds for divorce, achieving the highest score of 0.686. Following in descending order of effectiveness are Photographic evidence (A₃) with a score of 0.626, Electronic Messages (A₁) with 0.515, and lastly, Location Records (A₄), which was the least effective with a score of 0.067. This final ranking demonstrates that the model successfully integrated the judges' assessments across the four criteria while systematically processing the inherent uncertainty associated with each piece of evidence.

The neutrosophic approach is particularly useful in adultery cases, where direct proof is often scarce and the evidence presented carries high levels of indeterminacy and potential falsity. By considering not just truth but also these indeterminate factors, the OWA-TOPSIS model offers a more nuanced assessment than traditional methods. It stands as an effective tool for judicial authorities, providing a systematic and objective framework to evaluate competing and uncertain information. This enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of judicial decision-making and helps to lessen the evidentiary obstacles present in the Ecuadorian legal system.

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